

A Network Security Insight based on AI/ML for 5G Advanced & Beyond

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Abstract This paper provides an analysis of the emerging security risks and AI/ML (Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning) based solutions for 5G advanced and beyond. It outlines the current state of the art related to AI/ML enablers in 5G Advanced based on 3GPP Release 18 considering the radio and core network, network management and orchestration, as well as AI/ML empowered applications running on UEs (User Equipment). Furthermore, it examines how the AI/ML may evolve in 6G with the adoption of native AI elaborating the main concept and key features and provides a detailed overview of the 6G RIGOROUS architecture highlighting the emerging use of AI/ML in network security risk assessment and prevention through different design layers and operational mechanisms. A detailed analysis is then conducted considering the recent AI/ML based security solutions highlighting the key mechanisms and coordination requirements.

Index Terms—6G, 3GPP, AI/ML, Native AI, Security

I. INTRODUCTION

THE adoption of AI/ML techniques in 5G Advanced and emerging 6G systems, aims to enable optimizations, root cause analysis and new services leveraging the benefits of big data, which is already available in network operators premises. Field and service operations in the telco ecosystem account for 60-70% of the operating budget [1], wherein AI/ML will have a catalyst role in optimizing. Vertical services designed for 5G systems are progressively becoming more autonomous, e.g., considering massive IoT, vehicular, drones or Industry 4.0, and diverse blending of physical and cyber elements into new services such as metaverse [2]. Intelligence through AI/ML is a key enabler to handle the complexity of these emerging services and assures the desired service experience for the consumers. A comprehensive overview of the AI/ML algorithms and key enabler mechanisms are detailed in [3][4].

AI/ML enables the capability to learn without being explicitly programmed and can facilitate intelligent autonomous decisions in the mobile networks. However, the use of big data and AI/ML raises several issues for network operators in terms of where AI/ML shall be applied to achieve the maximum benefits and how to minimize the data collection without negatively affecting the performance of AI/ML. Another concern concentrates on the security risks since automation enables the network to self-operate to a certain extent and for various tasks with security attacks having potentially greater impacts especially when targeting AI/ML components and relevant operations.

This paper elaborates the current state of AI/ML features and enabler technologies considering the progress in 3GPP Release 18 related to 5G Advanced in terms of the radio and core network, network management and orchestration layer as well as UE (User Equipment) AI/ML empowered

applications. It then elaborates the concept of native AI pointing out the key enhancements compared to 5G advanced including elements that may impact the architecture development. In this context, the 6G RIGOROUS architecture brings new opportunities of using AI/ML to analyze and restrict security risks considering the dynamics of an emerging architecture and the way that security can be handled through different design layers and operational mechanisms. A set of AI/ML based security solutions are then detailed pointing out the key mechanisms and required coordination with other existing 3GPP based solutions.

The remaining of this paper is organized as follows. Section II provides an overview of the current state of the art regarding the adoption of AI/ML in 3GPP considering RAN, 5G core and management plane, and application. Section III elaborates the concept of native AI, while Section IV overviews the 6G RIGOROUS emphasizing security aspects. Section V analyses the main security solutions. Finally, Section VI provides a 6G outlook of AI/ML based security and concludes the paper.

II. OVERVIEW OF AI/ML IN 3GPP 5G SYSTEMS

3GPP with the advent of 5G Advanced has developed a set of enablers for AI/ML to facilitate intelligence in different parts of a mobile network. AI/ML has a distinct operational scope depending on which part of the network it is applied. AI/ML in the RAN (Radio Access Network) typically focuses on a single radio access point or a set of neighboring base stations.

For the 5G core, AI/ML enables optimizations for the operation of the control plane, while in the management layer it may focus on an individual domain or on cross domains basis (e.g., RAN and 5G core) to achieve resource optimizations, root cause analysis and network maintenance.

AI/ML may also assist the application layer in gaining a network insight for enhancing service quality or optimizing the applications running in UE without compromising privacy issues.

Figure 1: Overview of AI/ML applicability in 5G Advanced network architecture

An overview of the AI/ML applicability in the 5G advanced architecture is illustrated in Figure 1.

A. AI/ML in RAN

The general framework for AI/ML in 5G RAN is described in [5], which includes four main functions including: (i) data collection to provide input data for both running the AI/ML mode (i.e., for inference) and for model training, (ii) model training responsible for data preparation, (re-)training, validation, and testing, (iii) model inference provides the analytics output (e.g., predictions) to the consumer and feedback to the model training function indicating when re-training is needed (but this is out of scope of the RAN WGs), and (iv) actor (i.e., analytics consumer) that triggers an action based on the analytics output received from model inference, and provides feedback that influences the data collection process, assisting also the monitoring of the AI/ML model performance. The AI/ML in the RAN mainly focuses on three use cases:

- i) *AI/ML-based network energy saving* aims to reduce energy costs despite the continuous deployment growth of the RAN and the higher service demands without compromising users' performance. Energy saving can be achieved by cell deactivation, load reduction, coverage modifications or radio re-configuration. Mechanisms for energy saving need to consider several factors, including the cell load, RAN capabilities, KPI/QoS (Key Performance Indicator/Quality of Service) requirements, number of active UEs and UE mobility, cell utilization, etc. AI/ML can address key issues such as cellular load prediction, conflicting targets between system performance and energy saving, set and adjust target thresholds and supervise energy saving decisions beyond a local view. To balance the system performance and energy efficiency, AI/ML techniques can adjust dynamically the system

parameters based on predicted system performance, QoS and service KPIs for a given future time window.

- ii) *AI/ML-based load balancing* is an issue related to traffic growth. If traffic is not distributed evenly among cells, areas of cells, carriers, or RATs (Radio Access Technology), it results in congestion and service degradation. Traffic related to congested cells or areas can be offloaded to less congested cells with dynamic optimization of handover parameters and handover actions. Currently, load balancing decisions rely on present or past state cell load status. User experience and system capacity can be improved with AI/ML using predicted load status and UE analytics.

- iii) *AI/ML-based mobility optimization* related to service continuity and minimized radio link failures, call drops, unnecessary handovers, and ping-pong effects among neighboring cells. With the adoption of higher frequencies and decreased cell coverage, handovers occurrences increase, especially for high mobile UEs. AI/ML techniques can enhance Self Organizing Networks (SON) functions reducing the probability of unintended events (too late/too early handover, handover to a wrong cell), predict UE location and mobility for selecting handover cells and performing early data forwarding and traffic steering by adjusting handover parameters, considering dual connectivity.

B. AI/ML in 5G Core Network

AI/ML in 5G core is based on the introduction of a dedicated network function (NF) referred to as Network Data Analytics Function (NWDAF) for producing analytics, i.e., statistics and predictions [6]. NWDAF forms an integral part of network automation framework offering different types of analytics, such as NF load, UE mobility, communication patterns, QoS sustainability, etc., that operate within a specified geographical region defined by a set of tracking areas. The 5G core analytics can be classified broadly into two types: (i) UE related analytics and (ii) network analytics. Analytics in 5G core can be requested using an Analytics ID, indicating optionally the target UE(s), other filtering information, e.g., area of interest, and the reporting preferences.

Analytics consumers may subscribe to receive regular analytics results or can request and receive a single analytics report. NWDAF may provide analytics for any NF, management entity and applications, including consumers residing outside the operator premises, i.e., via the Network Exposure Function (NEF). 5G core analytics can interact with other domains, e.g., OAM (Operations, Administration, and Management), and are enhanced to support roaming, i.e., enabling an NWDAF that handles a UE related analytics to forward the data collected or analytics produced (i.e., UE context) to another pre-configured NWDAF in the visiting PLMN (Public Land Mobile Network) to assure analytics service continuity and precision. The NWDAF can collect data from various data source(s) including NFs, application functions and from the OAM. To handle efficiently the data

collection and prevent data sources from handling multiple subscriptions, the Data Collection Coordination Function (DCCF) is introduced. The collected data is formatted and processed by the DCCF by itself or using the Messaging Framework, which is also responsible for sending notifications to all specified data consumers and notification endpoints. The data collected and the produced analytics results can be stored for further use in an Analytics Data Repository Function (ADRF). The overview of analytics service operation supported by 5G core is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Overview of 5G core analytics operation

In 5G core, NWDAF may take the role of analytics inference by containing an Analytics Logical Function (AnLF) or model training incorporating the Model Training Logical Function (MTLF) or both. The NWDAF AnLF may request or subscribe to a selected NWDAF MTLF for obtaining model training and consecutive updates. To accomplish this, there is a need to introduce a Model ID and mechanisms to monitor model drifts, i.e., monitor the conditions to trigger model updates when the model performance decreases. The model drift can be monitored in the NWDAF MTLF by comparing predicted results with the ground truth data (i.e., actual measurements), or can be triggered from the NWDAF AnLF, which can receive feedback from the analytics consumer related to the accuracy of the provided analytics. Currently, NWDAF supports (un-)supervised model training and ensemble learning (i.e., using multiple models) in NWDAF MTLF as well as Federated Learning (FL), wherein certain NWDAF MTLFs act as clients that provide model training using the local data, while other NWDAF MTLFs take the role of the server aggregating the received local model updates. Analytics models can be stored in the ADRF for reuse with certain restriction applied, i.e., allowing only the producer vendor or certified entities from the producer of a model to reuse a stored model.

C. AI/ML for Management and Orchestration

AI/ML in the management and orchestration plane is introduced with the advent of Management Data Analytics (MDA) [7]. The focus of MDA is on resource management, configuration and feasibility check for configuring a network slice, network maintenance, fault management and root cause analysis as well as average UE performance (e.g.,

end-to-end latency, jitter, throughput). The MDA analytics results do not only contain statistics and prediction but also provide recommendations. MDA recommendations aim to identify the root cause of an issue (fault or congestion) and its location, which network resources are involved or shall be modified or put into energy saving or what mobility configuration (e.g., too early/too late) needs to be adopted among neighboring base stations, etc. MDA results are based on various input data as shown in Figure 3, including performance measurements and KPIs, MDT data, alarm information and configuration management data as well as on non-3GPP management data, UE location information via the Location Management Function (LMF) and analytics output from NWDAF (e.g., Service Experience).

Figure 3: Overview of MDA Architecture

Unlike NWDAF that specifies a network function, MDA defines an NRM (Network Resource Model) fragment, which enables a Management Service (MnS), i.e., a RESTful interface, for controlling analytics. A consumer may build an MDA MnS by using the CRUD operations, i.e., Create, Read, Update and Delete, together with the MDA control NRM (Network Resource Models) fragment. Initially, a consumer creates a “job” to receive analytics, which can be controlled via the NRM fragment that specifies: (i) the MDA type involved (i.e., the identifier of analytics), (ii) the scope of analytics, (e.g., target objects or area of interest), (iii) the preferred reporting method and (iv) the time schedule for receiving analytics results. Once an MDA “job” is created, the consumer may update it, e.g., by providing a new scope, or even terminate it using the Delete operation. Reporting analytics results can be: (i) file based, where the analytics results are inserted into a file before the MDA producer notifies the consumer to collect it, i.e., fetch it, (ii) streaming that requires the establishment of a connection before reporting analytics results once produced in a stream directly to the consumer, and (iii) notification based where the MDA producer notifies the consumer that the results are ready to be obtained from an indicated location. The MDA paradigm allows the consumer to filter the fields of analytics results needed, providing in this way flexibility in obtaining analytics without necessarily being obliged to receive the entire report but selected field only. To handle efficiently the data collection related to MDA a data collection, storage and distribution framework considered in the management plane. An MDA MnS producer that provides inference may trigger a model training request from an ML Training (MLT) entity

and provide the training data [8]. Alternatively, the MTL may initiate model training by evaluating the model regularly with newly collected data or considering observations of a new network status. A trained AI/ML model shall contain the training context (i.e., the network conditions of training) to allow a consumer to select the appropriate model based on the required use case.

D. AI/ML for Applications and in the UE

The adoption of AI/ML in UE for enabling various applications has raised network requirements as documented in [9] related to:

- i) *AI/ML model inference*: UEs have limitation in terms of the CPU and battery, and at certain cases they may be incapable to run an AI/ML model for inference. Being able to split a model between a UE and an edge platform and running inference in a combined manner is possible to resolve this issue provided that the network can support the required throughput and latency in the UL/DL(Uplink/Downlink), i.e., a new QoS profile, as specified in [10].
- ii) *Multi-model storage*: UEs may have certain ML models to use for different circumstances, e.g., peak-times or off-peak times, on the move or at specific locations, but the memory of a UE is limited to be able to store all of them at the same time. To resolve this issue, a UE may fetch an AI/ML model from an edge cloud platform when needed. To achieve this efficiently, i.e., in the required time and without disrupting other services, there is a need to check the network conditions and traffic during an AI/ML model transfer.
- iii) *Federated Learning (FL) model training*: Performing training at a UE for a specific AI/ML application may prove to be challenging because of data availability. To resolve this issue without compromising the requirements of privacy and data security it is easier to perform FL using local data and then aggregate local updates to create a global one. Since AI/ML involves training for an application the aggregation node can be an AF, but it still needs to rely on network assistance to get informed when it is the optimal time to perform FL training and which of the potential UE shall be used considering the network conditions and UE availability.

III. NATIVE AI

The notion of native AI is recently developed in the field of mobile networks and is a concept discussed for emerging 6G networks. Native AI takes the current AI/ML approaches a step forward in the sense that it drives the use of intelligence from simply a function or service that provides an insight to various consumer into an integral part of the network. Native AI may include several features including:

- i) *Embedded intelligence*, with AI/ML being a part of a function or a service. In other word AI/ML may enhance or even replace traditional mechanisms that deal with providing decisions, e.g., select a UDM, policy or network orchestration action.

- ii) *Self-learning intelligence*, allowing AI enabled functions, services, or protocols to adopt learning mechanisms to support maintaining the desired intelligence as a new feature.
- iii) *Coordinated intelligence* among NFs and services, or within a domain and cross-domain via the use of nested closed loops.
- iv) *Intent-based intelligence* assembles an automated processes that assures a business requirement, throughout the lifecycle of a service and translate it into network requirements and policies that can be applied consistently, by monitoring and adjusting the network resources.

The concept of native AI can be applied in various phases of a network service including network planning, service deployment and optimization, maintenance, and fault management. Native AI can be a part of a network equipment, service, protocol, domain, or device, e.g., UE, allowing AI to be used across different network components.

IV. 6G RIGOROUS ARCHITECTURE

The RIGOROUS “secuRe desIGN and deployment of trUsthwoRthy cOntinUum computing 6G Services” European project [11] is actively addressing the new cybersecurity challenges for devices, networking, and services. Within such a novel framework and architecture, new AI/ML mechanisms will be developed to react to dynamically changing threat surface on multiple layers of the network, including attack prevention, anomaly/intrusion detection, mitigation, and policy enforcement. A secure, trusted and privacy-conserving environment is the main pillar of the architecture to support the trustworthy continuum computing services with a full Dev-Ops lifecycle from onboarding of services and devices, up to the day-2 operations.

The Dev-Ops lifecycle uses AI/ML mechanisms in software design, protocols, and procedures as well as zero trust management by implementation. The RIGOROUS architecture is shown in Figure 3. The architecture comprises several security domains (i.e., in blue color) that are representing the SOAR (Security Orchestration Automation Response) closed loop approach with the functional blocks of monitoring and analysis, orchestration, management and reaction. To manage end-to-end services across multiple domains, the security management domains implement the functional blocks from the architecture to enable 6G secure by design and to enable trustworthiness in the overall network operations.

The architecture can be on a high-level distinguished in two modes of operation, the pro-active mode, triggered by the intent based security management, and the Reactive mode, triggered by the data monitoring and analytics functional block. Four functional blocks are using AI mechanisms and are highlighted here in more detail:

- i) *AI driven Security Analytics Engine (SAE)* detects policy violations, performs real-time network and security anomaly detection, communicates the results to the AI driven Decision functional block.

Figure 4: Overview of 6G RIGOROUS architecture

- ii) *AI driven decision* processes the data from the AI driven cyber physical correlator functional block and the privacy-preserving federated AI anomaly detection of the SAE; detects and identifies cyber threats or intrusion types, which are communicated to the AI driven security orchestrator.
- iii) *AI driven security orchestrator* enforces proactively or reactively the security requirements specified by the adopted security policies; provides self-healing and self-protection capabilities to the entire managed system with an AI-driven decision engine; triggers mitigation countermeasures in the AI driven response mitigation functional block.
- iv) *AI driven response mitigation* enforces the mitigation strategies in the system; provides two services: slice control service; AI-powered economic denial of sustainability mitigator service.

V. SECURITY SOLUTION

A. AI for Security

AI/ML is suitable to detect zero-day attacks that do not have a signature available for a traditional attack detection. Beside signature-based detection of cyberattacks, the anomaly detection verifies the deviation from the normal state of the system and flags potential attacks [12]. System monitoring is a prerequisite to gather the information on the status of the system in to perform further investigations on anomaly detection and root cause identification. The data and information which is monitored may be on different layers in the system, i.e., in general availability of resources, e.g., NFs load situation or resource utilizations and throughput as described in Section II.

The monitoring can also span into protocol states, malformed packets (header values out of range, new header parameters etc.) protocol failures and the respective error codes on different protocols such as RRC, PDCP, NAS, SBI etc. or on application layer in case operator native applications like SIP/IMS media are involved. Further

information can be collected on a per NF basis or in a more fine-granular way on a per UE basis, depending on the point of data collection. The 5G system can also collect data from the network management related to service events and network status, including performance measurements, KPIs, trace data (MDT reports), QoE (Quality of Experience) information, configuration data, alarms, and other network analytics data.

1) Anomaly Detection

Anomaly detection requires the definition on the normal state and behavior of a UE or system to draw a comparison to events or behavior that deviate from it. There is some basic anomaly detection already defined within the scope of the network analytics. Specifically, NWDAF can identify a group of UEs or a specific UE with abnormal behavior, where abnormal is defined in the sense that the UE is hijacked, misused, or running malicious applications [6].

The NWDAF can provide analytics on the following two analytics types based on the exception identity parameters:

- i) *Mobility related analytics*: Unexpected UE location, ping-pong across neighboring cells, unexpected wakeup, unexpected radio link failures.
- ii) *Communication related analytics*: Unexpected long-live, or large rate flows, unexpected wakeup, suspicion of DDoS attack, wrong destination address, too frequent service access.

Upon detection of abnormal behavior based on the analytics of the exception identity parameters, the NWDAF informs the consumer.

Malformed packet detection is another kind of anomaly detection, which requires the comparison of a packet format received with the expected packet format considering the information elements and the allowed range of values [10]. Any deviation, e.g., not allowed information elements or non-allowed value would result in a malformed packet. The receiver of the malformed packet should simply drop it. The malformed packet can be used by an attacker intentionally to exploit in a specific implementation version and perform

3GPP 5GA	Security Issue	Method	RIGOUROUS Security	RIGOUROUS Advancements
Anomaly detection	UE behavior / Packet	Correlation assuming knowledge of normal state	AI driven SAE	Real-time security control
Trust security	UEs	Authorization, authentication once UE attaches to network	AI driven decision	Continuous trust evaluation, quantification, verification
Root cause analysis	NF, MnS, UE	Policy enforcement for security	AI driven security orchestrator	Intent based security
-	-	-	AI driven response mitigation	Mitigation reaction plan

Table 1: RIGOUROUS security added value advancements compared to the 3GPP 5GA Rel-18 security features.

further attacks, e.g., privilege escalation.

2) Root Cause Identification

MDA may perform root cause analysis related to security issues [13]. An MDA MnS producer can collect data from both 5G core and network management and may correlate it to explore if the behavior of 5G core NFs match the one described from the performance measurements and KPIs provided by the management plane. A mismatch, e.g., a high cell load indication without UEs residing on a specific cell, or frequent relocations of virtual NFs, may trigger a security risk event. MDA may assist in identifying the domain, the type of security issue, the objects involved and provide recommendation to resolve it.

3) Security Policies

Security policies are used to steer the level of security on the radio interface between a UE and a base station for a specific Packet Data Unit (PDU) session, i.e., user plane traffic [10]. With the security policy the confidentiality and/or integrity protection of the user plane traffic is activated for all Data Radio Bearers belonging to the PDU session. The security policy can take three values each for confidentiality and integrity, i.e., “not needed”, “required” or “preferred”. With “not needed” no protection is activated, with “required” the protection is mandatory and the PDU session is released if the security policy cannot be fulfilled and “preferred” is best effort in activating the protection.

4) Intent based Network Operation and Security

Intent based network allows a mobile network operator or a 3rd party service provider to define the instructions towards a network as business KPI, which can be translated by the network entities intuitively into real-time network actions [14]. The network can continuously monitor the operations of the defined intents and provides operation adjustments to ensure alignment with the given intent. Intents can significantly improve the network security, e.g., if an intent is defined as ‘Distributed denial of service attack reduction by 5% at a specific network entity’, then a related action can be executed autonomously by the network to count the number of incoming service requests or messages exceeding the configured limits, records the abnormality and takes mitigation actions, e.g., to release the connections that cause the flooding attack. Similarly, a wide range of intents can be defined specific to different security control measures and network domains, to enable the network to safeguard and implement autonomous security and prioritization policies.

VI. 6G OUTLOOK AND CONCLUSION

AL/ML are poised to play a significant role to enable an intelligence especially on security, but its use needs to become more AI native to handle the challenges of 6G. As the configuration and optimization of networks currently relies on a model-based approach, that may fail to adopt for dynamic and complex 6G networks due to scale, density, and heterogeneity. Security limitations are numerous as illustrated in Table 1, which shows the advancements of a native AI architecture based on RIGOUROUS. Pervasive AI/ML can leverage 6G with potential breakthrough in enabling distributed AI/ML at the network edge for model training, process optimizations, privacy, and data security handling [15].

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